

GUIDELINES FOR TEACHERS ON THE USE OF GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY CLASS MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS

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Abstract. *In the content of this article, attention is paid to the effective aspects of game technologies and the important aspects that can be more effective in order to give instructions for teachers regarding the use of game technologies in the lessons of primary language and reading literacy.*

Keywords: *game, game technologies, pedagogical process, level of education and upbringing, psychology of individual development of the student, formation of the personality of the student.*

The level of education and training in school is largely determined by the degree to which the pedagogical process is oriented to the psychology of the child's age and individual development. It includes psychological-pedagogical study of schoolchildren during the entire period of study in order to determine the individual development opportunities and creative abilities of each child, to strengthen his positive activity, to reveal the uniqueness of his personality, to provide timely help in case of lagging behind in studies or unsatisfactory behavior. This is especially important in the lower grades of the school, when the purposeful learning of a person is just beginning, when learning becomes a leading activity, when the child's mental characteristics and qualities, first of all, cognitive processes and attitude towards himself as a subject of knowledge (cognitive motives, self-esteem, ability to cooperate, etc.) are formed in his bosom.

Games are the main activity of students, especially elementary school students. Games are an important tool in forming the personality of students. In it, the student is formed in every way. It has a positive effect on the results of the educational process. Games have educational aspects, such as concentration of attention, strengthening of memory, complete thinking, being kind to each other, valuing the team, loyalty, aspiration, evaluating each other's opinion. In addition, in the process of the game, it creates an environment for students to form a team, establish cooperation and friendship, communicate, and agree. This will make the students more united.

If today, in the course of lessons based on the National Curriculum, games aimed at the same positive efficiency are organized in the lessons of the mother tongue and reading literacy, these games will encourage students to think in all aspects. They are also very useful for the educational process. It serves to increase the quality and content of education, and to form competences related to the subject and subject.

At the same time, it should be said that the use of didactic games in providing grammatical knowledge of the mother tongue and reading literacy to elementary school students gives effective results. Because a child of primary school age is still not separated from play activities. Elementary school students learn a number of phonetics. Vowels and consonants are distinguished based on pronunciation and comparison. They will get practical knowledge about voiced and unvoiced

pronunciation of consonants, paired and unpaired voiced and unvoiced consonants. In this regard, the testing method used in elementary grades allows to understand whether sounds are voiced or voiceless. This, in turn, helps in writing correctly. Also, in these classes, he gets practical knowledge about syllables and their types, stressed and unstressed syllables, and the effect of sounds on each other. Mastering all this creates a number of complications. Because of this, it is useful to use didactic games related to science or, in a word, specifically phonetics, in elementary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes.

The development of cognitive interests depends not only on the skills of the teacher, but also on his methodological preparation. It should not be forgotten that the leading activity of young students is play.

Currently, game technologies are one of the unique forms of education that not only make the work of students interesting and exciting at the creative and research level, but also allow them to learn the mother tongue and reading literacy, as well as other subjects. The game helps to add emotional color to the monotonous activity of memorizing, assimilating, and repeating information. Another positive aspect of the game is the application of acquired knowledge in a new situation. Thus, mastering new material occurs through practice and arouses interest in the learning process.

The relevance of the game for modern schoolchildren is obvious as it is presented in a bright form and is filled with information that does not require reflection or additional work. Now the subject-information environment is expanding all over the world. Computer networks and television bring a lot of different information about school students. Therefore, the first task of the school is to develop self-assessment and selection of received information. And one of the forms that develop these skills is the game. It is worth noting that teaching students, especially elementary school students, through games, the teacher teaches not in a way that it is convenient to give the material to the students, but in a way that it is more convenient for the students to learn it.

Education in primary school is the basis of the further education process. If a student learns the simplest concepts in elementary school, then complex topics will be given to him easily in higher classes. Every teacher is interested in the good results of students in learning. 6-9 year old students are not interested in studying dry theory. Therefore, it is not inappropriate to recommend teachers to use game technologies to make lessons lively and memorable in primary education.

The traditional approach to teaching focuses on the average level of education. The problem is that the standard presentation of the subject in primary education causes students to lose interest in learning. They continue to go to school because they have to. At the same time, students try to get good grades to get a new toy or initial praise from their parents. For this reason, game technology in primary education is aimed at increasing students' interest in basic subjects. These subjects are mathematics, mother tongue and reading literacy, writing, foreign and Russian languages.

The main purpose of game technology in primary education is to encourage children to learn. In the course of recreational activities, the student's creative personality is formed, he learns to systematize the acquired knowledge and use it to solve various problems in the future. Another goal of the game is to strengthen the physical and mental health of students. Pupils learn to communicate in a team in an active form. Many games also include light physical activity. And as a result of this, the emotional upsurge that appears in students helps to strengthen their "I". Such

games are games that help overcome student complexes. This is especially important for students who lack self-confidence. That is, it helps teachers a lot in working with such students.

In accordance with the state educational standard, each game technology used in the lesson processes organized in the subjects related to primary education must solve certain tasks. These are the following tasks:

- development of children's ability to think independently;
- solving simple problems without external help;
- achieving full mastery of the subject material by every student in the school team;
- maintaining the physical and mental health of children during the educational process.

The teacher who teaches each elementary school team should know exactly these tasks and should not forget it in practical processes.

All games that can be used in the educational process are divided into groups: educational, developing, reproductive, diagnostic.

Each type has a specific task. During the educational game, the student learns information that he did not know before. The development of educational game technologies is focused on identifying new abilities in the student. In such lessons, the teacher teaches students to think logically. Reproductive games help to consolidate the learned material. In addition, in such lessons, the teacher will find out where there are gaps, what material the students have not fully mastered. Regardless of the type, each didactic game has a clear structure and should include the following: players' roles, game actions, plot.

Two main methods can be used to improve the learning process in primary education: role-playing games in the classroom, as well as competitions. The latter option encourages students to learn more. Every student wants to learn to be the best. Thus, game pedagogical technologies should be used continuously from the main educational process. There should be a surprising effect. A teacher can achieve the best result if he combines traditional education with games. Game technology in primary education should become a priority in organizing the educational process for young children.

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